

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Oxidation of Secondary Alcohols by Hexamethylenetetramine-Bromine[†]

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Oxidation of secondary alcohols by hexamethylenetetramine-bromine (HABR) in acetic acid leads to the formation of the corresponding ketones. The reaction is first order with respect to HABR. Michaelis-Menten type kinetics were observed with respect to alcohols. The oxidation of benzhydrol- α -d exhibited a substantial kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 3.16$ at 298 K). The reaction was subjected to both polar and steric effects of the substituents. A mechanism involving transfer of a hydride ion from the alcohol to the oxidant has been proposed.

Hexamethylenetetramine-bromine (HABR) has recently been reported as a synthetic reagent for the oxidation of alcohols to carbonyl compounds and for the regeneration of carbonyl compounds from oximes and hydrazones^{1,2}. Only a few reports regarding the mechanistic aspects of the reactions of HABR are available in the literature^{3,4}. There seems to be no report on the oxidation of secondary alcohols by HABR. Therefore in the present paper, we report the kinetics of oxidation of eight aliphatic secondary alcohols, 1-phenylethanol and benzhydrol by HABR in acetic acid solution. Attempts have been made to correlate rate and structure in this reaction. Mechanistic aspects are also discussed.

Results and Discussion

The rate and other experimental data were obtained for all the alcohols investigated. Since the results are similar, only representative data are documented here.

The reactions are of first order with respect to HABR. The reaction rate increases with an increase in [alcohol] but not linearly (Table 1). A plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{alcohol}]$ is linear ($r > 0.990$) with an intercept on the rate ordinate. Thus, Michaelis-Menten type kinetics were observed with respect to the alcohols. This leads to the postulation of following overall mechanism, [eqns. (1) and (2)] and the rate law (3),

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 K [\text{alcohol}] [\text{HABR}] / (1 + K[\text{alcohol}]) \quad (3)$$

The dependence of k_{obs} on the [alcohol] was studied at different temperatures and the values of K and k_2 were evaluated from the double reciprocal plots. The thermodynamic parameters of the complex formation and activation parameters of the decomposition of the complexes were calculated from the values of K and k_2 respectively at different tem-

peratures (Tables 2 and 3).

To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of benzhydrol- α -d (PhCDOHPh) was studied. It was observed that the formation constants of the complexes of ordinary and deuteriated benzhydrols had similar values but the rate of decomposition of the complexes showed a considerable primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 3.16$ at 298 K). Addition of HXA resulted in an increase in the rate of oxidation (Table 1).

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANT FOR THE OXIDATION OF 2-PROPANOL BY HABR AT 298 K

$10^3 [\text{HABR}]$ mol dm ⁻³	[PrOH] mol dm ⁻³	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ s ⁻¹
1.0	0.10	4.57
1.0	0.20	7.44
1.0 ^a	0.40	10.9
1.0	0.60	12.8
1.0	0.80	14.1
1.0	1.00	15.0
1.0	2.00	17.2
1.0	3.00	18.1
2.0	0.40	11.1
4.0	0.40	11.8
6.0	0.40	10.6
8.0	0.40	11.5
1.0	0.40	10.3 ^a
1.0	0.40	19.7 ^b

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile. ^bContained 0.02 mol dm⁻³ HXA.

The linear correlation between log (rate) at 288 and 318 K for the oxidation ($r^2 = 0.9983$) shows that an isokinetic relationship exists in the oxidation of alcohols by HABR⁵. The value of the isokinetic temperature is 881 ± 12 K. An isokinetic relationship is a necessary condition for the va-

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

lidity of linear free energy relationships. A linear isokinetic relationship also implies that all the alcohols are oxidized by the similar mechanism.

In solutions, HABR may dissociate to form molecular bromine,

The probable oxidizing species in a solution of HABR are, therefore, HABR itself, bromine and its acetolysis product. However, strict first order dependence on HABR and the rate-enhancing effect of HXA rule out both bromine and its acetolysis product as the reactive oxidizing species. Hence HABR itself is the reactive oxidizing species in the reaction.

A perusal of uv-vis spectra of HABR (0.001 mol dm⁻³) and an equivalent amount of bromine (0.002 mol dm⁻³), in acetic acid at ≈293 K, showed that the difference in the nature of the spectra of HABR and bromine was not very striking but their optical densities showed variations. HXA had no appreciable absorption in this range. Further, the spectrum of HABR did not show any change in the experimental time period (*ca.* 2 h). When a solution of HABR in acetic acid was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure, HABR was recovered unchanged. This confirmed that HABR retained its identity in acetic acid.

The data in Table 2 show that the formation constants of the alcohol-HABR complexes are not much sensitive to the nature of the substituent in the alcohol molecule. The rate of decomposition of the complexes (Table 3), however, showed considerable variation.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF HABR-RCHOHMe COMPLEXES AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Subst.	K (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹)				ΔH kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
Me	3.55	2.94	2.40	1.81	-19.1±0.9	-47±3	-5.12±0.7
Et	4.15	3.57	3.01	2.50	-15.3±0.5	-33±2	-5.51±0.4
Pr	3.36	2.70	2.11	1.62	-20.9±0.6	-54±2	-4.91±0.5
i-Pr	3.93	3.28	2.61	2.00	-19.6±0.9	-48±3	-5.36±0.7
iso-Bu	4.53	3.90	3.31	2.65	-15.9±0.8	-34±3	-5.83±0.6
Bu	3.15	2.60	2.05	1.57	-20.2±0.8	-52±3	-4.79±0.7
ClCH ₂	3.52	2.85	2.21	1.66	-21.5±0.9	-56±3	-5.02±0.7
MeOCH ₂	4.31	3.68	3.02	2.35	-17.8±0.9	-41±3	-5.66±0.8
Ph	4.77	4.08	3.44	2.78	-16.1±0.7	-35±2	-5.94±0.5
Benzhy- drol	3.85	3.26	2.72	2.11	-17.6±0.9	-41±3	-5.38±0.7
Benzhy- drol- α -d	4.30	3.68	3.03	2.38	-17.6±0.8	-41±3	-5.67±0.6

Correlation analyses of reactivity : The rate constants

TABLE 3—RATE CONSTANT AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF THE OXIDATION OF RCHOHMe BY HABR

Subst.	$10^4 k$ (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^* kJ mol ⁻¹
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
Me	0.86	2.01	4.71	11.0	62.1±0.8	-108±3	94.0±0.7
Et	1.55	3.59	8.44	19.3	61.5±0.8	-105±3	92.6±0.6
Pr	3.20	7.10	14.8	35.8	57.9±1.0	-111±5	91.0±1.0
i-Pr	5.62	12.4	26.5	60.1	56.9±1.0	-110±4	89.5±0.9
iso-Bu	11.2	23.8	50.0	108	57.3±1.0	-109±4	89.5±0.9
Bu	3.65	7.96	18.4	38.8	54.8±0.9	-112±3	87.9±0.7
ClCH ₂	0.012	0.033	0.088	0.23	57.8±0.8	-110±3	90.6±0.6
MeOCH ₂	0.12	0.31	0.75	1.83	67.6±1.0	-105±3	98.7±0.8
Ph	13.4	27.7	51.5	98.8	47.8±0.5	-134±2	87.7±0.4
Benzhy- drol	16.6	35.4	68.2	138	50.5±0.6	-122±2	87.0±0.5
Benzhy- drol- α -d	5.14	11.2	21.9	44.8	52.0±0.6	-128±2	89.9±0.5
k_H/k_D	3.23	3.16	3.11	3.08			

of the decomposition of the aliphatic alcohols-HABR complexes failed to yield good correlations separately with Taft's⁶ σ^* and E_s values [eqns. (5) and (6)]. The correlation with σ^* values accounts for *ca.* 93% of the data but the correlation is not acceptable by Exner's criterion⁷,

$$\log k = -2.07 (\pm 0.23) \sigma^* - 3.48 \quad (5)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9305; \text{sd} = 0.27; n = 8; \psi = 0.20$$

$$\log k = -1.73 (\pm 1.13) E_s - 4.19 \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.2785; \text{sd} = 0.87; n = 8; \psi = 0.73$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ the Exner's statistical parameter⁷. The rates were, therefore, correlated in terms of the Pavelich-Taft⁸ dual substituent-parameter equation,

$$\log k_2 = \rho^* \sigma^* + \delta E_s + \log k_0 \quad (7)$$

The values of the substituent constants were obtained from the compilation by Wiberg⁸. The correlations are excellent; reaction constants being negative (Table 4). There is no significant collinearity ($r^2 = 0.2136$) between σ^* and E_s of the eight substituents.

The negative polar reaction constant indicates an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state of the rate-determining step. The negative steric reaction constant shows

TABLE 4—TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF THE REACTION CONSTANTS

T/K	ρ^*	δ	r^2	sd	ψ
288	-1.98±0.01	-0.94±0.01	0.9999	0.005	0.01
298	-1.90±0.01	-0.90±0.01	0.9998	0.004	0.01
308	-1.84±0.01	-0.85±0.01	0.9998	0.014	0.02
318	-1.79±0.02	-0.82±0.12	0.9997	0.009	0.01

a steric acceleration of the reaction. This may be explained on the basis of the high ground-state energy of the sterically crowded alcohols. Since the crowding is relieved in the product ketone as well as in the transition state leading to it, the transition state energies of the crowded and uncrowded alcohols do not differ much and steric acceleration, therefore, results.

The faster oxidations of 1-phenylethanol and benzhydrol may well be due to stabilization of the electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state by phenyl groups through resonance.

Mechanism : The observed rate law suggests the formation of an intermediate in a rapid pre-equilibrium. Similar observations were recorded earlier in the oxidation of primary alcohols and aldehydes as well^{3,4}. The intermediate complex may be formed by the interaction between the non-bonded pair of electrons of alcohol-oxygen and HABR. The formation of similar complexes has been postulated in the oxidation of alcohols by pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide¹⁰. The presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 3.16$ at 298 K) confirms that the α -C-H bond is cleaved in the rate-determining step. The large negative value of the polar reaction constant together with the substantial deuterium isotope effect indicated the presence of a highly electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state. Therefore a hydride ion in the rate-determining step is postulated. A nonlinear transition state, implied in a hydride-ion transfer via an intermediate complex, is supported by the relatively low magnitude of kinetic isotope effect also. The mechanism depicted in Scheme 1 accounts for all the experimental results. The mechanism is supported by the observed negative entropy of activation also. As the charge separation takes place, in the transition state of the rate-determining step, the charged ends become highly sol-

Scheme 1

ated. This results in an immobilization of a large number of solvent molecules, reflected in the loss of entropy.

Experimental

All the alcohols (commercial, Fluka) were dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and then fractionated. Benzhydrol was recrystallized from ethanol. HABR¹ and benzhydrol- α -d (PhCDOHPh¹¹) were prepared by the reported methods. Isotopic purity of PhCDOHPh, as ascertained by its nmr spectra, was $94 \pm 5\%$. Acetic acid was refluxed with chromic acid and acetic anhydride for 6 h and then fractionated.

Product analysis : The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions, i.e. with an excess of the alcohol over HABR. In a typical experiment, 2-propanol (0.05 mol) and HABR (0.01 mol) were made up to 100 ml in acetic acid and kept in dark for ca. 10 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The solution was then treated with an excess (200 ml) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm⁻³ HCl and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was dried, weighed, recrystallized from ethanol and weighed again. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallization were 2.17 (91%) and 1.92 g (79%) respectively. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and m.m.p.) with the DNP of acetone. Similar experiments were performed with other alcohols also. The overall reaction may therefore be written as

Kinetic measurements : Reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by maintaining a large excess of the alcohol ($\times 15$ or more) over HABR. The solvent was glacial acetic acid. The reactions were carried out at constant temperature (± 0.1 K) and were followed upto 80% reaction by monitoring the decrease in [HABR] at 394 nm. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were computed from linear ($r > 0.990$) least-squares plots of log [HABR] vs time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$ (Table 1). The second order rate constants (k_2) were evaluated from the relation, $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{alcohol}]$.

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References

1. I.YAVARI and G. SHAABANI, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1994, 274.

2. B. P. BANDGAR, S. B. ADMANE and S. S. JARE, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1998, 154.
3. A. PAREEK, S. KOTHARI and K. K. BANERJI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1996, **35**, 970.
4. A. PAREEK, S. VARSHNEY and K. K. BANERJI, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1997, **60**, 127.
5. O. EXNER, *Collect. Chem. Czech. Commun.*, 1966, **31**, 3222.
6. R. W. TAFT in "Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry", ed. M. S. NEWMAN, Wiley, New York, 1956, Chap. 13.
7. O. EXNER, *Prog. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1973, **10**, 411.
8. W. A. PAVELICH and R. W. TAFT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 1957.
9. K. B. WIBERG, "Physical Organic Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1963, p. 416.
10. D. MATHUR, P. K. SHARMA and K. K. BANERJI, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1993, 205.
11. N. S. SRINIVASAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1974, **30**, 419.